

EVALUATING PEAK AREA UNCERTAINTIES IN CONNECTION TO PASSIVE GAMMA MEASUREMENTS OF SPENT NUCLEAR FUEL

V. SOLANS¹, H. SJÖSTRAND¹, P. JANSSON¹, S. GRAPE¹,
P. SCHILLEBEECKX², A. SJÖLAND^{3,4}

¹ *Department of Physics and Astronomy, Uppsala University,
Ångströmlaboratoriet, Lägerhyddsvägen 1, 751 20 Uppsala, SWEDEN*

² *EC-JRC-Directorate G, Unit G.2,
B-2440 Geel, Belgium*

³ *Swedish Nuclear Fuel and Waste Management Company,
Stockholm, Sweden*

⁴ *Division of Nuclear Physics, Lund University,
SE-221 00, Lund, Sweden*

June 2, 2022

ABSTRACT

In many countries, spent nuclear fuel is planned to be stored in a geological repository. Before the final encapsulation, safety parameters such as decay heat, criticality, and dose rate need to be ensured. A gamma scan of the spent nuclear fuel assemblies in the pool can extract valuable information needed to verify or update the declared values before the encapsulation. Gamma scans can be used to estimate values such as burnup, cooling time, or initial enrichment [1], but also decay heat [2]. This paper presents results from a full-energy peak area evaluation study of experimental gamma-ray spectra acquired from measurements using a high-purity germanium detector on 47 spent nuclear fuel assemblies from Sweden in 2016 and 2019. The assemblies chosen are UO_2 fuel and represent a large span in cooling-time, burnup, and initial enrichment [3]. The gamma spectra were acquired in the spent fuel pool of the Clab facility. As part of the measurement analysis, one wishes to determine the full-energy net peak areas associated with selected fission products. This work presents results obtained using different methods to evaluate the full-energy peak areas, including the use of different background estimations.

In the determination of important safety parameters using gamma spectroscopy, it is crucial to consider uncertainties originating in the peak area analysis. The uncertainty from the full-energy peak area without the background has been evaluated and compared between the different models.

1 Introduction

For many countries, such as Sweden, it has been proposed to store highly radioactive waste in a geological repository [4]. To ensure the safety of the repository for geological time scales, safety and design conditions must be fulfilled. The spent nuclear fuel assemblies in Sweden are coming either from pressurized water reactors (PWRs) or boiling water reactors (BWRs). Once the spent nuclear fuels (SNFs) have cooled down after outtake from the reactor core, they are transported and placed in water ponds at the Clab facility, located near Oskarshamn, which is a national interim storage facility where SNFs are stored [5]. The proposed final repository is a geological one where the SNFs will be stored in copper canisters [5]. Once all canisters are placed in the geological repository, the remaining space is backfilled with bentonite [5]. The geological repository is based on a multi-barrier system which includes the engineered canister then the rocks (bentonite and host rock). In Sweden, 11'000 tonnes of spent nuclear fuel is expected for the final repository, representing approximately 5'600 copper canisters [5]. The current copper canister design allows for a maximum of 4 PWR or 12 BWR fuel assemblies. The SNFs position and orientation are carefully calculated in order to fulfil the safety and design requirements. Some limitations are the multiplication factor, the decay heat, the gamma and neutron dose rates for instance. Experimental validation of calculations are needed to calibrate and validate calculations, before the encapsulation. For instance, count rate of some radionuclides extracted from passive-gamma scans on SNFs can be used to validate calculated gamma dose rate or the decay heat [2]. In this study, the objective is to estimate the uncertainty in the peak area determination of those radionuclides from the SNFs using results of passive gamma-ray measurements. In particular the uncertainty coming from the parameters of the models will be investigated, and compared for the different models.

In 2016 and 2019, two gamma scans measurement campaigns at Clab were performed, on Swedish SNFs [3]. The SNFs were scanned axially using a high purity germanium detector (HPGe). The analysis of these gamma scans involves determining full-energy peak areas and their corresponding uncertainty for the safety parameters needed to be computed. Careful discrimination between the signal and the background is not trivial. In this paper, only the Cs-137 peak are be studied, as it is the dominant radionuclide in spent nuclear fuel with cooling time between 10 to 30 years [6].

This study is structured as follows; Section 2 is the description of the fuel assemblies and set up used for the measurements. Section 3 presents the different models to compute the full-energy peak area, in particular the functions used to describe the signal and background contributions. The results of the study are in Section 4 where the comparison of the uncertainty from the full-energy peak area determination without the background for the different models is presented.

2 Fuel data and measurement campaign information

2.1 Fuel assembly information

The assemblies measured in both measurement campaigns are part of the SKB-50 assemblies. The SKB-50 assemblies are a set of assemblies carefully selected to represent a large range of initial enrichments, burnups and cooling times in the Swedish SNF inventory. Different NDA measurement techniques have been used to measure these fuel assemblies, thereby creating a unique collection of data [3, 6, 7]. Among these 50 assemblies, half of them are PWR SNFs and the other half are BWR SNFs. For the PWR SNFs, the initial enrichment ranges from 2.1% to 4.1%, the burnup ranges from 20 to 53 GWd/tU [8] and the discharge year varied from 1984 to 2009 [3]. The PWR fuels are either of 17x17 or 15x15 type and are coming from different commercial vendors [3]. For the BWR SNFs in the SKB-50, the initial enrichment spans from 1.3% to 4.0%, the burnup ranges from 9 to 46 GWd/tU [8] and they were discharged from the reactor between 1985 to 2006 [3]. The BWR SNFs also come from different commercial vendors and are of different geometries (both 10x10 or 8x8).

2.2 Experimental setup used for the measurement campaigns of 2016 and 2019

The measurements took place in 2016 and 2019 at Clab in Sweden. [3]. The raw data of each SNF is available in Ref. [3]. The SNFs located in the pool were vertically scanned, using a HPGe detector, as detailed in Ref. [6]. The detector comes from Canberra Industries, model GX4018. It is equipped with cryostat model CP5-Plus-SL and preamplifier model 2002CSL. The data was acquired using Lynx from Canberra Industries. A Cs-137 calibration source was positioned

along the line of sight of the detector during all measurements (SNFs and background) [3]. There are 166 gamma spectra available from the 50 different SNFs, facing the detector with different corners.

3 Models description used to evaluate the full-energy peak area

In this section, two different approaches to determining the full-energy peak are described. One approach involves the use of fitting functions to describe the background and signal components, while the other one builds on numerical integration of signal counts above the background level.

3.1 Energy spectrum

In Ref. [3] the assemblies were measured continuously during the axial scan, also during part of the recording when the assembly is not in front of the detector. The time window selection allows taking into account only counts when the assembly was in front of the detector. If the total measurement time was taken into account, the total count rate would be much lower as the background can represent a large proportion of the measurement time. For each spectrum measurement, it is one corner that is facing the collimator slit. During the recordings, for each batch (group of measurement) a live-time, where the dead-time has been compensated for, is associated with the real-time. Therefore the dead time is already corrected in the spectra studied in this paper. Fig. 1 is an example of a collected energy spectrum obtained. In Fig 1, the x-axis corresponds to the energy deposited by the photon in the detector, expressed using ADC-channels as well as energy. For the energy calibration from ADC-channel to keV, it has been assumed that the peak with the highest count rate corresponds to the full-energy peak of Cs-137 decay at 662 keV. This energy calibration is not used in this study but added in this figure for comprehension purpose.

Figure 1: Total count rate for the SNFs: PWR01, corner 135.

3.2 Full-energy peak area determined by the peak fitted models

For the determination of critical safety parameters, information on the full-energy peaks in a gamma spectrum is required. One way to obtain such information is to describe the peak(s) using mathematical functions. The signal part of the full-energy peak can often be described using a Gaussian function, but sometimes a tailing function is also required to fully describe it. In addition, the peak is often located on a continuous background, which also needs to be described and subtracted before the peak information can be determined. One component of the background is due to the Compton continuum resulting from the detection of gamma-ray with a higher energy [9]. The full peak-fitting model can thus be described using a function describing the sum of the gamma-ray peak ($P(x)$), the background ($B(x)$) and a tailing function ($T(x)$) if needed.

In this work, the function "fit" in the lmfit package in Python has been used for the peak analysis Ref. [10]. The method is fitting the data with either 'leastsq' or 'least_squares' depending on which method gives the smallest χ^2_{ν} value (see section 4.1).

3.2.1 Full-energy peak

The signal part of the full-energy peak is here proposed to be described using a Gaussian function and a tailing function.

3.2.1.1 Gaussian function

The full-energy peak is described with a Gaussian function, see Eq. 1.

$$P(x) = a_1 \cdot \exp(-(x - \mu)^2/\sigma^2) \quad (1)$$

where a_1 is a scale parameter, μ is the mean value of the peak, and σ is related to the width of the peak. x are the channels of the spectrum (proportional to the energy deposited).

This function has been largely used in literature to describe full-energy peaks in gamma-energy spectra Ref.[9].

3.2.1.2 Tailing function

As Knoll writes in Ref. [9]: 'Tailing can arise from several physical effects, including imperfect charge collection in some regions of the detector, or secondary electron and Bremsstrahlung escape from the active volume'. As a result, a lower energy than the full-energy peak are recorded for some photons in the detector. In this study, the tailing term is included in the full-energy peak area. The tailing function from Ref. [11] is shown in Eq. 2. For some spectra, no tailing terms are necessary and for others, one is needed.

$$T(x) = a_3 \cdot (\exp(B(x - \mu))) \cdot (1 - \exp((-1/\sigma^2)(x - \mu)^2)) \cdot \delta \quad (2)$$

where a_3 is a scale parameter, μ is the mean value of the Gaussian peak, and σ is related to the width of the peak. B is a fixed parameters of the tailing function linearly dependent on the full-energy peak area. (Avoiding to have B as a free parameter allows to stabilize the fit). δ takes the value 1 when $x < \mu$ and 0 when x is above μ . x are the channels of the spectrum (proportional to the energy deposited).

Fig. 2 is an example where a tailing term is needed to best describe the data, consisting of a Gaussian function, a tailing function and a background described by an error function.

Figure 2: Cs-137 full-energy peak of PWR01 with a fit consisting of a Gaussian function, a tailing function and a background described by an error function. The background and the tailing terms are shown with the dotted line in blue and black.

The tailing is not always required to describe the data. It is only needed when the Gaussian peak is unable to fit properly the low-energy edge of the full-energy peak that an additional component such as a tailing function is required. Therefore, in Section 4 it is determined for each spectrum if the tailing term is needed or not.

3.2.2 Background function

The background is modeled as *erfc* function and a constant. The *erfc* function models the Compton scattered gamma-rays under investigation, i.e., the one that creates the full-energy peak. I.e, even if these Compton scattered gamma-rays have the same origin as the full-energy peak, they are commonly attributed to the background, since they are not part of the full-energy peak. The *erfc* function is the result of a convolution between a step function and a

Gaussian peak Ref. [12]. The contribution to the background from gamma-rays originating from other sources or processes are described with a constant function. The background function is defined in Eqs. 3 and 4

$$B(x) = a_2 \cdot \text{erfc}((x - \mu)/\sigma) + \text{constant} \quad (3)$$

$$\text{erfc}(x) = 1 - \frac{2}{\sqrt{\pi}} \int_0^x e^{-t^2} dt \quad (4)$$

where a_2 is a scale parameter, μ is the mean value of the Gaussian peak, and σ is related to the width of the peak. x are the channels of the spectrum (proportional to the energy deposited).

3.3 Full-energy peak area determined by numerical integration

As a second approach, peak area determination using numerical integration is discussed. In this approach, the background is subtracted from the signal and subsequently all signal counts are summed. I.e., after a fit, the background is subtracted, channel by channel from the counts and the full-energy peak area is approximated by summing the counts left. Hence, the challenge is to find the best description of the background. In this work, three different methods to estimate the background are discussed: the best fitted model as determined in the previous section, a linear background and the background function determined using only the edges of the full-energy peak. Note that numerical method are good only when full-energy peaks are easy separable, therefore not always applicable.

3.3.1 Numerical integration using best fitted model, NI_{BFM}

For this method the background is simultaneously fitted together with the peak as in section 3.2. I.e., the background level is determined from the best fitted model (the model that fits the data the best between the one with or without the tailing term).

3.3.2 Numerical integration fitting background using only edge channels, NI_E

In this method, a sequential fit of the peak and the background is performed. First the full spectrum is fitted similar as in in Section 3.3.1. Subsequently, the parameters defining the the full energy peak are fixed. Finally, the background parameters (*erfc* function and constant value) from Section 3.2.2 are fitted using only the edge channels. By first defining the peak and subsequently fitting the background in a region where the spectrum is dominated by the background, a better fit to the background can be obtained. Since the *NI* (Numerical Integration) methods only need a good method to define the background level, this method is considered to be best practise and is the reference method for the paper.

3.3.3 Using linear background

Instead of determining the background using a fitted model that tries to reproduce the physics of the background, it is not uncommon to simply represent the background with a linear function. The parameters of the linear function are only determined using the edge channels of the spectrum.

4 Results

4.1 Criterion for model selection for fitted models

There is a need to determine which fit is performing best for each spectrum in order to determine the number of counts in the full-energy peak of Cs-137. In particular, it is of interest to know if there is a need for a tailing term or not.

In order to select which fit perform the best, one can look at the reduced chi-squared value (will be called chi-squared value for the rest of the paper for simplicity), well known to evaluate the goodness of a fit (χ^2_ν).

For each of the 166 gamma spectra available in Ref. [3], two fits were applied (Gaussian peak and *erfc* background without/with tailing function). The best model for each gamma spectrum is determined from the smallest χ^2_ν value. The Fig. 3 displays the distribution of the difference between the two χ^2_ν values obtained from the fits with or without tails for all of the 166

spectra. A positive difference indicates that the fit with the tailing function has a smaller χ_ν^2 compared to without tailing term. Out of the 166 spectra, only 32 had a χ_ν^2 smaller without the tail but the difference in these χ_ν^2 is at a maximum 0.64. Whereas for spectra with a very high count rate, having a tailing term in the fit largely improves the χ_ν^2 value. One can also observe that the different background id (different measurement campaigns with various attenuation plates, presented in Ref. [3]) also seems to influence the preference of the tailing term or not. It is coming from the choice of the detector during the different measurement campaigns.

Figure 3: Difference in χ_ν^2 between the fitted models with or without tailing function. A positive difference means that the fit with tails has a lower χ_ν^2 than the model without tail.

Figure 4: Cumulative histogram of χ_ν^2 for all fitted models and 166 gamma spectra of Ref. [3].

It is also possible to look at the cumulative histogram of the χ_ν^2 for all gamma spectra in Fig. 4. It is clear that it is not wise to choose a model and apply it blindly to all spectra because in some cases another model will better fit the data. The highest χ_ν^2 values are fitted models without the tailing term. Like in Fig. 2, adding a tail term can significantly improve the fit. Detailed comparison and recommendation are presented in Section 4.3.

4.2 Peak area evaluation and uncertainty

First, the full-energy peak was fitted using one of the models (with or without the tailing function). The fit of the models was performed using the fit function of the Imfit package in Python Ref. [10]. Once the parameters of the models have been found, one can evaluate the counts of each channel with the model and remove the background.

In order to evaluate the uncertainty in the full-energy peak area, one needs to take into account the uncertainty coming from the parameters estimated with the fits. For that, the covariance was extracted from the result of the fit. The Jacobian of the fitted functions was calculated using the SymPy Python's library [13]. The uncertainties in the full-energy peak area value were calculated using Eq.5.

$$\text{Area uncertainty} = \sqrt{J_{\text{Area}} * J_{\text{Parameters}} * Cov * J_{\text{Parameters}}^T * J_{\text{Area}}^T} \quad (5)$$

where Cov is the covariance matrix of the parameters of the fit given by the "fit" function of the Imfit package in Python Ref. [10]. $J_{\text{Parameters}}$ is the Jacobian of the fitted model with respect to the parameters of the fit. J_{Area} is the Jacobian of the function that described the peak area, with respect to the predicted count per channel. This is one of the methods that can be used to account for a non-perfect parameterisation of the data (see Eq. 5).

To compute the uncertainty for the numerical integration methods, it was decided to use again Eq. 5, and the square root of the total area, see Eq. 6.

$$\text{Area uncertainty} = \sqrt{(\sqrt{\text{total area}})^2 + (\text{uncertainty from Eq.5})^2} \quad (6)$$

For the numerical method NI_E , the ratio between the $\sqrt{\text{total area}}$ and the uncertainty from Eq.5 is compared (see Eq. 6). In average, the $\sqrt{\text{total area}}$ is 1.43 higher than the uncertainty from Eq.5. The minimum ratio in the 166 spectra is 1.08, and the maximum ratio is 1.63. Therefore in all the spectrum the $\sqrt{\text{total area}}$ component of the uncertainty is the bigger.

It is then possible to compare the full-energy peak area calculated by the different models. Each peak area evaluation has been normalized to the value of the numerical integration using the best fitted method and for each spectrum.

In Fig. 5 and Tab. 1 one can observe that the fit with the numerical integration using a linear model sometimes estimates a larger peak area than the other methods, like the best fitted model or other numerical integration. This is due to the fact that this model doesn't well represent the physics and failed to represent in particular, the edges the full-energy peak. This method is sometimes used because it is simple to apply [14].

In section 3.3.1, the model used to describe the background for each fuel assembly, is selected based on the (lowest) χ^2_ν value. (So it is the Gaussian peak, the background function and possibly the tailing function). By using this knowledge, the numerical integration (NI_{BFM}) described in section 3.3.1 uses this method to discriminate the background.

The numerical integration using only the edges of the full-energy peak (NI_E) to fit the background is then used as a reference method to the other fitted model in Fig. 5 and Tab. 1. The advantage of such method is to ignore the shape the full-energy peak.

As expected, the numerical integration using the best-fitted model (NI_{BFM}) is closest to the reference model, NI_E (the closest to 1) as their methodology is the most alike, see shown in Tab. 1.

Figure 5: Cumulative histogram for the normalized full-energy peak area with respect to the numerical integration using the edges of the full-energy peak for each spectrum.

	Mean	Std
Numerical integration using the linear background	1.0023	0.0025
Numerical integration using the best fitted model	0.9987	0.0018
Best fitted method	0.9950	0.0035

Table 1: Mean and standard deviation (std) of the normalized full-energy peak relative to the numerical integration using the edges of the full-energy peak for each spectrum.

Figure 6: Ratio of the numerical integration using the best fitted model (cf Sect. 3.3.1) to the numerical integration using the edges (cf Sect. 3.3.2) for the full peak area depending on the χ^2_ν .

One can see that in Fig.6, the difference between the numerical integration using the best fitted model (NI_{BFM}) and the numerical integration using the edges (NI_E) is within 0.2% for 73% of the spectrum measurements and within 0.5% for 95% of the spectrum measurements. For low χ^2_ν values the differences in the full peak area are negligible. Whereas, for the χ^2_ν above 10, the deviation can reach up to 1%.

For the best fitted model, compared to the numerical integration using the edges (NI_E), the difference between 0.2% drops to 20% and within 0.5% to 57%. The maximum difference even reached 2%.

4.3 Comparison between uncertainties between the different models to evaluate the full-energy peak area

Concerning the relative uncertainty, one can observe in Fig. 7 that the fitted models (black and red crosses) have significantly lower uncertainties. Indeed the numerical integration methods the main term comes from the $\sqrt{\text{total area}}$ compared to the uncertainty from Eq.5 that is only used in the fitted methods (cf discussion following Eq. 6 in Section 4.2). (The numerical integration using only the edges (NI_E) is the reference method). Notice that for $\chi^2_{\nu} \gg 1$, the uncertainty from the fitted models can no longer be trusted because they are not able to reproduce the data sufficiently, which is the case for most of the spectra in this study (see Fig. 4).

For the numerical method using the best-fitted method (NI_{BFM}), the uncertainty is similar to the numerical uncertainty using only the edges (NI_E). However NI_E uses only the channels on the edges of the full-energy peak therefore the number of data points to determine the background is reduced, which slightly increased the uncertainties.

Figure 7: Ratio of the full-energy peak area uncertainty for all models with respect to the numerical integration using only the edges (NI_E).

Figure 8: Relative uncertainty of the full-energy peak area uncertainty for all models

On Fig. 8, one can observe the relative uncertainty for all the models. As expected from Fig. 7, NI_E is the method that has the higher uncertainty. It decreases when the full-energy peak area, because the counting statistics improves (mainly the term $\sqrt{\text{total area}}$). At maximum the uncertainty is 0.6% for the reference, and 0.2% in average. The relative uncertainty in 8 can be fitted to a exponential relation depending on the full-energy peak area which is: $\text{Relative uncertainty [\%]} = (\text{Full-energy peak area})^{-0.4844} \cdot 112.1$.

5 Conclusion

The aim was to compute the full-energy peak area of the SNF gamma scan data provided by Ref. [3]. In order to compute the full-energy peak area, different models have been compared. The full-energy peak has been described using either a Gaussian function and possibly a tailing function together with different background models, or using numerical integration of signal counts with different background models. The reduced chi-squared values has been used to evaluate the performance and select the best fitted model. It tends to indicate that the tailing term should be used when fitting a spectrum but also that preferences depends on the detector used. The uncertainty coming from the parameters of the fitted models and the uncertainty due to pure counting statistics were compared for full-energy peak area Cs-137 from Ref. [3]. On average, the numerical integration gives higher uncertainties than the other methods tested in this study on the full-energy peak area after subtraction of the background. However other methods such as the fitted models has uncertainties that cannot be trusted for $\chi^2_{\nu} \gg 1$. Therefore this method (integration using only the edges, NI_E) should be used in similar cases. In this study, only uncertainties from the counting statistics have been studied. However, other sources would need to be considered when using the area of full-energy peak in an SNF spectrum for quantitative analysis, such as positioning of the SNF or the setup's geometry.

Acknowledgement

The project leading to this paper has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 847593.

References

- [1] C. Hellesen et al. "Nuclear spent fuel parameter determination using multivariate analysis of fission product gamma spectra". en. In: *Annals of Nuclear Energy* 110 (Dec. 2017), pp. 886–895. ISSN: 03064549. DOI: 10.1016/j.anucene.2017.07.035. URL: <https://linkinghub.elsevier.com/retrieve/pii/S0306454917302220> (visited on 03/24/2020).
- [2] P. Jansson et al. "Gamma-Ray Spectroscopy Measurements of Decay Heat in Spent Nuclear Fuel". en. In: *Nuclear Science and Engineering* 141.2 (June 2002), pp. 129–139. ISSN: 0029-5639, 1943-748X. DOI: 10.13182/NSE02-A2272. URL: <https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/full/10.13182/NSE02-A2272> (visited on 01/04/2021).
- [3] Peter Jansson et al. "Time stamped list mode data from gamma-ray spectroscopic measurements on 47 nuclear fuel assemblies performed at Clab, Sweden, September 2016 through March 2019". en. In: *Data in Brief* 31 (Aug. 2020), p. 106039. ISSN: 23523409. DOI: 10.1016/j.dib.2020.106039. URL: <https://linkinghub.elsevier.com/retrieve/pii/S2352340920309331> (visited on 08/07/2020).
- [4] Svensk Kärnbränslehantering AB. *Design and production of the KBS-3 repository*. Technical Report TR-10-12. 2010. URL: <http://www.skb.com/publication/2167363/TR-10-12.pdf>.
- [5] "Plan 2019. Costs from and including 2021 for the radioactive residual products from nuclear power – Basis for fees and guarantees for the period 2021–2023". en. In: (), p. 55.
- [6] S. Vaccaro et al. "PWR and BWR spent fuel assembly gamma spectra measurements". en. In: *Nuclear Instruments and Methods in Physics Research Section A: Accelerators, Spectrometers, Detectors and Associated Equipment* 833 (Oct. 2016), pp. 208–225. ISSN: 01689002. DOI: 10.1016/j.nima.2016.07.032. URL: <https://linkinghub.elsevier.com/retrieve/pii/S0168900216307707> (visited on 03/25/2020).
- [7] Alexis C. Trahan et al. "Results of the Swedish spent fuel measurement field trials with the Differential Die-Away Self-Interrogation Instrument". en. In: *Nuclear Instruments and Methods in Physics Research Section A: Accelerators, Spectrometers, Detectors and Associated Equipment* 955 (Mar. 2020), p. 163329. ISSN: 01689002. DOI: 10.1016/j.nima.2019.163329. URL: <https://linkinghub.elsevier.com/retrieve/pii/S0168900219315621> (visited on 09/23/2020).
- [8] Stephen Joseph Tobin et al. *Nondestructive Assay Data Integration with the SKB-50 Assemblies - FY16 Update*. en. Tech. rep. LA-UR–16-28290, 1330638. Oct. 2016, LA-UR–16-28290, 1330638. DOI: 10.2172/1330638. URL: <http://www.osti.gov/servlets/purl/1330638/> (visited on 12/10/2020).
- [9] G. Knoll. *Radiation Detection and Measurement*. Journal Abbreviation: New York, John Wiley and Sons, Inc., 1979. 831 p. Publication Title: New York, John Wiley and Sons, Inc., 1979. 831 p. Jan. 2000. ISBN: 0-471-07338-5.
- [10] Matthew Newville et al. *LMFIT: Non-Linear Least-Square Minimization and Curve-Fitting for Python*. Sept. 2014. DOI: 10.5281/ZENODO.11813. URL: <https://zenodo.org/record/11813> (visited on 05/03/2021).
- [11] R.Gunnink. *MGA: A gamma-ray spectrum analysis code for determining plutonium isotopic abundances*. Tech. rep. Apr. 1990. URL: <https://www.osti.gov/servlets/purl/6738453>.
- [12] Klaus Debertin and Richard G. Helmer. *Gamma- and x-ray spectrometry with semiconductor detectors*. Amsterdam ; New York : New York, NY, USA: North-Holland ; Sole distributors for the USA and Canada, Elsevier Science Pub. Co, 1988. ISBN: 978-0-444-87107-7.
- [13] Aaron Meurer et al. "SymPy: symbolic computing in Python". en. In: *PeerJ Computer Science* 3 (Jan. 2017), e103. ISSN: 2376-5992. DOI: 10.7717/peerj-cs.103. URL: <https://peerj.com/articles/cs-103> (visited on 05/03/2021).

- [14] Peter Jansson et al. "Axial and azimuthal gamma scanning of nuclear fuel - implications for spent fuel characterization". In: *Journal of Nuclear Materials Management* 45.1 (2016), pp. 34–47. URL: https://resources.inmm.org/system/files/jnmm/vol_45/V-45_1.pdf.